

1 Title:

2 Recommendations to improve the process of PA guideline development, monitoring adherence,
3 and future evidence.

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5 Authors:

6 V. T. van Hees^{1,2}, W. Wendel-Vos³, M. J. Chinapaw¹

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8 ¹Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Department of Public and Occupational Health,
9 Amsterdam Public Health research institute, The Netherlands.

10 ²Accelting, Almere, The Netherlands

11 ³ National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Bilthoven, The Netherlands

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15 **Abstract**

16 In this discussion article we discuss the role that PA guideline committees may play in
17 improving the monitoring of adherence to PA guidelines, and how physical researchers and
18 method developers can support this effort.

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20 **Main text**

21 Physical activity (PA) guidelines inform society about the minimum required PA level
22 required for physical and mental health benefits. This is the basis for PA policies, multimedia
23 campaigns and (tailored) PA promotion programs. Guidelines also provide a benchmark for
24 monitoring PA levels and identifying risk groups, see Figure 1.

25 However, when developing PA guidelines several challenges arise. The first challenge is
26 making sure that the PA guideline represents the current state of evidence relating PA to health.
27 The second challenge is how to communicate the benefits of PA to the general public with
28 practical and feasible examples. The third challenge is the assessment of PA levels for
29 monitoring adherence. This commentary focusses on the third challenge; how to assess
30 adherence to PA guidelines.

31 There are numerous methods available to assess PA. Thus, each particular project can
32 select the most suitable measurement method. This severely hampers comparability between
33 studies as well as various (national) surveillance systems [1]. This methodological diversity
34 makes that PA guidelines are typically derived from a highly heterogeneous evidence base.
35 Moreover, PA guidelines are never accompanied by an instruction on how to measure adherence

36 [2–5]. We propose that PA guidelines should be accompanied with an operational definition of
37 how to assess adherence. For example, steps per day is an ambiguous concept until we
38 operationalise it with a specific device counting steps that decides for us which body movements
39 are counted as steps and which are not. The current lack of such an operational definition
40 weakens the guidelines: Imagine a guideline on safe levels of radiation that leaves doubt about
41 the definition of radiation and how it is quantified. This would hamper protecting the population
42 from radiation risks.

43 We argue that this is not so much a methodological challenge, but a consensus challenge.
44 PA guideline committees are in the best position to identify the main methods in research that
45 underpin their proposed PA guidelines. Therefore, it becomes a logical step to also select those
46 methods as recommended methods for monitoring adherence. Given that multiple different
47 methods have been used in the evidence underlying PA guidelines, the committee needs to
48 decide which methods were the strongest drivers of their guidelines. Narrowing the list of
49 methods down to a single recommended method seems impossible. However, it may be possible
50 to at least shorten the list e.g., one recommended questionnaire, or one algorithm for each of the
51 most common accelerometer placements per age group. This should not be mistaken as a
52 recommendation for how to assess PA in general, it will only provide guidance on how to assess
53 PA guideline adherence. If the PA guidelines are mainly based on exercise interventions then the
54 operational definition could be verified engagement in exercise similar to such interventions.

55 The above-mentioned proposal comes with several advantages: 1) It clarifies what
56 methods have been used for arriving at the PA guidelines, which in turn can guide ongoing
57 efforts to improve these methods, 2) it clarifies how the committee that defined a guideline
58 envisions the monitoring of adherence.

59 Take for example the 2020 WHO guideline on physical activity and sedentary behaviour
60 for children and adolescents. Here, Chaput and colleagues summarized the evidence on the
61 association between physical activity, sedentary behaviour, and health-related outcomes to
62 inform the new guideline [5]. The manuscript identified no reviews of high quality and four
63 systematic reviews on PA and health outcomes with a moderate quality rating. Three of these
64 reviews focused on PA interventions ranging from resistance training[6], to active lessons [7]
65 and school-based PA programs [8]. Another review focused on objectively-measured activity
66 patterns including studies using a large variation in definitions of activity patterns. The PA
67 guideline committee could formulate an operational definition for adhering to the PA guideline:
68 assessing whether a child engaged in PA similar to the most common effective interventions
69 included in the reviews. Further, the operational definition may be specified per age group.

70 To support PA guideline committees, we encourage PA researchers to not only report on
71 adherence to current guidelines but also present data that can inform future guidelines and clearly
72 describe the method and analytical approach. Secondly, we encourage PA guideline committees
73 to actively seek collaboration with methodological experts to work on a recommendation for
74 assessing adherence to PA guidelines. Finally, we encourage PA method developers to
75 communicate clearly what a method can and cannot capture.

76 In summary, we recommend PA guideline committees to provide information on the
77 main methods in research that underpin their proposed PA guidelines and clear guiding
78 principles on how to evaluate adherence to the proposed guidelines. We hope this will contribute
79 to a stronger evidence base for PA guidelines and a more transparent and homogeneous
80 monitoring framework.

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82 **Declarations**

83 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

84 Not applicable.

85 **Consent for publication**

86 Not applicable.

87 **Availability of data and material**

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89 **Competing interests**

90 The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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123 **Figure legends:**

124 Figure 1: Physical activity guideline development cycle

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